

MARKETING OF HIGHER EDUCATIONAL SERVICES: AN EMPIRICAL STUDY OF STUDENT’S PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract

In an era of technological advancement and wide availability of information about almost everything it is enormously important to address the marketing strategies and practices being employed for marketing of higher educational services. The recent massive expansion of education through private provision has introduced new horizons for marketers at the same time with the increase in number of educational institution continuously the competition is also increasing with same pace; it is surprising that more attention has not been paid to marketing issues that have been aroused as a result of increasing competition. Some of the burning issues such as are educational institutions really “customer-oriented”? Do they choose the most appropriate market segments? Would higher education marketers are practicing the most appropriate strategies to attract and recruit students? And the complexities of the decision processes of the “buyers” have to be addressed at war level. In this research paper we look first at general issues facing educational marketers, and then efforts would be employed to understand the students (Consumer) expectation and factors that attract them towards a particular institution. We also examine the marketing practices being employed by educational Institutions to attract and admit students; certain contemporary and valuable strategies have been suggested on the basis of findings to higher education institutions to survive in the competitive and turbulent environment.

Keywords: *E-Marketing, Educational Service Provider, Higher Education, Interdisciplinary, Market Preference, Relationship Marketing Strategy, Services Marketing*

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1. Introduction

Higher education is education provided by universities and other institutions that award academic degrees, such as university colleges, and Liberal Arts College (en.wikipedia). In presence of stiff competition and ever changing environment it has become a fashion for every organization to gain competitive advantages. Competition is everywhere; educational service sector is not an exceptional case. Population explosion fuelled by various educational policies of government for inclusive growth intensified competition in this sector. These changes have an effect on how higher education institutions operate nowadays and they are seen as the driving forces for the marketization of higher education (Maringe, 2006). For instance, the privatization of higher education and cost sharing through the introduction of tuition fees in many European countries (Voss, Gruber, Szmigin, 2007; Maringe, 2006) have increased the „consumerist” approach to higher education and the need to consider students’ expectations more. Or, the strengthening of competition at institutional, national and international level (Sizer, 2001; Baird, 1998) requires new operating modes through the adoption of more market oriented and business like forms of operation within higher education institutions.

To survive in the stiff and turbulent competitive market, educational institutions, particularly the institutions offering professional course like MBA, M.Tech, BBA, B.Tech, etc. are not lagging behind. They have also adopted practicing marketing their products and services. Sometimes they are not practicing customized marketing approaches for surviving in the competitive market. As per the GATS, Higher Educational Services include education services leading to a university degree or equivalent. Such education services are provided by universities or specialized professional schools. The programmes not only emphasize theoretical instruction, but also research training aiming to prepare students for participation in original work (GATS). Societies have a profound and long-term interest in their higher education institutions that extend beyond the pecuniary and short-term interests of current students, faculty, and administrators.

The third world countries currently have a weak higher education system. While globalization, technological and demographic changes, and the growing economic importance of knowledge are making higher education reform more urgent and challenging than in past, some of these factors are also making such reforms potentially more attainable (IBRD/world bank 2000).

2. Scope of the Study

The scope of the study has been limited to educational services marketing only. The study has been confined to Delhi & NCR region as this area has greater number of institutions of higher learning and students from all across the country.

3. Objectives

1. To study and analyze the current marketing practices being employed by higher educational Institutions
2. To find out the factors that affects the choice of institutions by students
3. To find out the marketing stimuli that attracts the students towards a particular institution
4. To suggest marketing strategies for higher educational Institutions to survive in cut throat competition

4. Research Methodology

The study is based on descriptive research design. A questionnaire has been designed, to know the point of view of respondent regarding the factors that helps students (consumers) in decision making. First part of the questionnaire contains information regarding demographics of the respondent. Second part has series of close-ended indirect questions which are based on students (Consumers) on student's emphasis as far as selection of educational institution is concerned. The survey was conducted in higher secondary schools, colleges and universities in Delhi & NCR, responses of 500 students were collected. We targeted 12th Class and graduation final year students to know how they are deciding on their admission and selection of institution. So the sampling technique used was non-probability convenience sampling. For visual representation of finding and results bar charts, pie charts and tables etc. ahs been used.

5. LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Criteria for marketing and advertising and their schemata in education have evolved out of historical social practices (**Alam, 2008; Ssesanga, 2004**). Interpretation of social events is guided and constrained by the prevailing rationality, which itself reflects the dominant constellation of power. Lately, the operation of a business without being involved in marketing activities is virtually impossible. As such, they ignored the role of formal advertising through media and felt that advertising was required only by those manufacturers whose products were substandard. Nowadays, such a concept is considered out of date (**Eunec Conference, 2003**). Every type of business, from the multinational company to the humble street grocer, gets involved with marketing (**Kotler, 2006; Hirtt, 2005**). Highlighted below are some of the more general advantages and disadvantages of marketing and advertising.
2. Historically, people had no prior knowledge when modern, scientific products were introduced. Then the advertisement and promotion of new goods made people aware, helping them to avail themselves of and benefit from their use (**Lynch, 2006**). It can be said that an improved quality of life has been attained from the utilization of scientific innovation and technological advancement. This has become possible because of the rigorous marketing and promotional activity carried out by public and private initiatives. Education has now come to be considered as a fundamental need to be pursued, thanks to rigorous campaigning and promotion (**Alam, 2008**).
3. Good communications between customer and producer help recognition of a product's existing quality and can help identify any further need for development. Advertising and promotion not only provides the details of a product, but information as to how it should best be used. This increases benefits after a comparatively small investment of money and time (**Kotler, 2006; Lynch, 2006**). Within this context, advertising and promotion can act as the link between producer and customer.
4. Customers will change their choice of product if the quality is not of the standard noted from advertising by the manufacturer or service operator. Ergo, producers have to take care to ensure the product quality is as stated in the advertising. Falling short of the required standard may lose the market partially or even totally, as competitors will always note any advertising distributed by their competitors to make their own product and promotion policy-rich (**Coulson, 2003**).

5. Successful advertising and promotion can often create intense interest from consumers wishing to consume/use the product. **Lynch (2006)** asserts that customers remain keen to buy a product when affected by 'advertisement craze'. This situation creates a money market that breaks the 'money fridge' (**Alam, 2008**). A country with more idle money suffers from a 'liquidity crisis', which may hinder development. Thus, the 'money market' caused by the advertisement/promotional activity helps with the country's development (**Kotler, 2006; Svensson, 2002**).
6. Historically, publicly funded media was the only tool for promoting recreation. Then, after a time, media providers began to earn significant sums of money from their commercials (**Morzyk, 2008**). This income reduced the pressure on public subsidies. More recently, the media has been fully controlled by private funding, with the largest portion of it gained from advertising income. In addition to providing financial support to the media, advertisements or commercials circulated for marketing purposes can also support alternative forms of recreation (**Kotler, 2006; Hirtt, 2005**). Producers may also choose to sponsor sports and other educational or recreational activities, which in turn subsidize the state budget for recreation.
7. Marketing activities can consume a large proportion of a company's total budget. For example, advertising consumes 72% of Coca-Cola's budget (**Coulson, 2003**). Within current practices, soft drink producer such as Coca-Cola are eager to compete with each other for a marketing 'show down', which does not essentially focus on the product itself, but will help the consumer be more alert to the finite details of their particular product and identify user benefits more readily (**Kotler, 2006; Svensson, 2002**). This type of competition does not create new markets (**Lynch, 2006**).
8. Production of a quality product requires significant levels of funding. As a result, the quality of the product itself and service levels remain secondary. Conversely, an advertising campaign that consumes a higher proportion of the money available is considered to be the first option for marketing purposes. A parallel investment towards quality control as well as advertising and promotion needs large amounts of funding, so that producers and service providers can put their efforts into advertising and not into quality control (**Coulson, 2003**).
9. Advertisement and promotional activities connected to social development and awareness give high priority to ethics and civic values. A commercial business will concentrate on increasing profits. In order to catch their target market, producers use eye-catching advertisements that might have a negative impact on social ethics and values (**Hirtt, 2005**). For example, while state and donor agencies put their best efforts into ensuring students follow lessons in detail, the advertising and promotional policies adopted by some organizations (that is, Ice-cream Company, publishers of story and cartoon books) are committed to teach an attitude that interrupts the students' concentration on the lesson.
10. In some countries, a number of problems are caused by advertisements that contradict the national aims and objectives may be noticed. For instance, **Morrow and Barraclough (2003)** finds that, while the government in Malaysia and the Philippines are committed to reducing the number of people who smoke, unsurprisingly, cigarette companies do not support the government. The vigorous marketing campaigns carried out by cigarette companies put the government's efforts into a 'wastage box'.

11. According to **Alam (2008)** the culture of Southern Asian countries is rapidly becoming more of a western pattern. He identifies that private education entrepreneurs support and promote the practice of western culture through their marketing activities. These days, producers do not just market their products, but also promote western culture in order to catch the attention of the potential client. Practice of different types of culture within one geographic boundary and having same kind of religious faith may restrict the building of a distinct national character (**Lynch, 2006**). Without a national character, achieving desired levels of development is constrained.
12. The concept of branding is not a new phenomenon. However, the marketing of brands is a relatively recent concept. These days, branding is obsessive and many producers choose not to sell their products under their own name, but prefer to seek the help of a particular brand for marketing purposes. This usually results in a higher price for the product, which will limit the consumption capacity of underprivileged groups (**Coulson, 2003**).
13. There is another type of brand marketing, which does not provide details of product and benefits but focuses on the identity of producers and sellers. For instance, a number of universities do not focus on the quality of the course and the part it plays in national development while carrying out promotional activities. They concentrate on promoting their name and the eminent persons involved with their establishment. Hence, we may note that some social services and awareness activities, as well as education, health, and gender equality, require marketing as social responsibility (**Holbrook, 2005**).
14. But unfortunately, many of the universities are doing business using the 'innocent ignorance' of students through ostensible brand marketing policy. This may be of benefit to the university and the individual who pursues the course, but ultimately contributes very little towards state development. It also provides inverse returns, as the time and money invested to gain such an education is a poor investment (**Alam, 2008**).

6. MARKETING PRACTICES AND TOOLS USED BY THE PROFESSIONAL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

Although nonprofit higher education at large has been slow to adopt many practices that are standard in the corporate setting, some areas of the academy, such as the business office, information technology, and student housing have taken great strides in this area. From methods of investing the endowment to implementing purchasing procedures to outsourcing operations such as the bookstore and construction and management of apartment-style residence halls, the functional areas that oversee these efforts have blazed a trail that has made more people within higher education at least familiar with, if not comfortable with or accepting of, ways of doing things that seem new and foreign.

Marketing theories and concepts, which have been effective in business, are gradually now being applied by many universities (Hemsley–Brown & Oplatka, 2006; Temple & Shattock, 2007) with the purpose to gain competitive advantage.

The higher education sector has two main features that influence, the marketing ideas that can be applied to it. First of all higher education in most countries is a non-profit sector, therefore marketing concepts applied to the sector do not function as in the business sector, where the primary goals is profit making. Second higher education is a service; therefore all peculiarities applicable to the marketing of services apply to higher education.

Figure: 7P's of Service Marketing

Taking into discussion the *targeted markets* in higher education, it is highly accepted that the sector has multi-clients, as students, employers and society are seen to be the main beneficiaries of higher education services (Maringe, 2006). Even though the whole notion of students as consumers attracts criticism (Hemsley–Brown & Goonawardana, 2007), students are the direct and immediate customers of the higher education services. Employers, too, benefit of the „results” of the higher education processes, as they use the skills and the abilities that graduates acquired during their studies. Some called graduates „products” of higher education, while the employers were seen as customers (Kotler & Fox, 1985; Conway et al, 1994), but we consider that both students/graduates and employers are consumers of higher education services. While students are principal consumers (Stensaker & D’Andrea, 2007), employers can be seen as secondary or indirect consumers of higher education services. Finally the society as a whole gets benefits of the results of the higher education.

The three categories are seen as the main stakeholders of higher education and as the main clients, with the students being the primary ones. Furthermore, there are other stakeholders, that have an interest in higher education: along, students, employers and society, there are also the parents, the government and other funding bodies, quality assurance agencies and other reglementing authorities, professional bodies (Chapleo, 2004; Voss, Gruber, Szmigin, 2007; Kantanen, 2007). Sometimes the needs and the wants of the different stakeholders do not totally coincide and higher education has to satisfy more constituencies, making its activity more complex. Students as primary clients are usually segmented and treated differently, but all other stakeholders are more difficult to segment. Soutar and Turner (2002) identified for UK three major student market segments: international students, mature students, and high school leavers,

segments with different motivations when making their higher education choice and different needs and wants from educational services.

Consumer behaviour in our case refers to student behaviour, as primary client and stakeholder of higher education, and it is one aspect worth studying. Aspects such as student expectations and student choice are characteristic to consumer behavior in higher education. Students’ expectations are seen as a valuable source of information (Sander et al, 2000), as their satisfaction depends on the relationship between their expectations and their perceptions of the actual performance. Similarly, knowing the reasons applicants choose universities and courses of studies, is important to developing institutional positioning (Maringe, 2006). Applicants to higher education are no longer passive consumers; they became informed consumers who make rational choices of higher education courses and institutions (Baldwin & James, 2000). Research in higher education choice by examining the decision making process and potential students’ search for information takes usually place (Hemsley–Brown & Oplatka, 2006), illustrating the application of these marketing concepts to the higher education sector.

However, the specificity of higher education is that most students (undergraduates) are one time consumers (Temple & Shattock, 2007); as opposed to the business sector where repeat purchases take place often. This result in differences in consumer’s behaviour in the two sectors and possible different marketing strategies to address consumers in the two sectors.

The very essence of institutional positioning is to differentiate itself from competitors. This is rather difficult to do in the higher education, as academic products are seen to be rather similar in UK (Temple & Shattock, 2007) and differences between universities as seen as not being decisive in Finland (Kantanen, 2007), while it is accepted that there is a lack of real differentiation in the sector in general (Chapleo, 2004).

Fig: Marketing tools used by educational institutions

7. Analysis

Table 1. Demographical Characteristics of the Respondents

Gender of respondent				
	Freque ncy	%	Vali d %	Cumula tive %
Male	368	73.6	73.6	73.6
Female	132	26.4	26.4	100
Respondent Age in Years				
17-19 Years	103	20.6	20.6	20.6
19-21 Years	176	35.2	35.2	55.8
21-23 Years	144	28.8	28.8	84.6
23 and above	77	15.4	15.4	100.0
Highest Educational Qualification				
Interme diate	188	37.6	37.6	37.6
Pursuin g graduati on	136	27.2	27.2	64.8
Pursuin g P.G.	99	19.8	19.8	84.6
P.G. and above	77	15.4	15.4	100.0

The results of demographical characteristics of the respondents show that out of 500 respondents 368 i.e. (73.6%) were male and 132 i.e. (26.4%) were female. While 320 (64%) of the

respondents were in between age of 19 – 23. The respondents who belong to Intermediate and Bachelor degree level are 324 (59.8).

It was found that 423 i.e. 84.6% of total respondents use News paper, Internet and college websites as the major sources of information to search a college of their choice.

Table 2: Factors affecting the choice of institution

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Infrastructure	188	37.6	37.6	37.6
Faculty Members	136	27.2	27.2	64.8
Placement assistance	99	19.8	19.8	84.6
Fees structure	77	15.4	15.4	100.0

Table 2 shadows that Infrastructure, Faculty Members and Fee structure are the major factors affecting the choice of institute.

Table 3 Ranking of decision factors

	Rank	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Recognitions from government bodies	I	121	24.2	24.2
Quality of education	II	110	22.0	22.0
Placement assistance	III	90	18.0	18.0
Scholarship/Financial Assistance	IV	87	17.4	17.4
Branding/Ranking	V	63	12.6	12.6
Transport and Residential facilities	VI	29	5.8	5.8

Table 3. Shows that students have ranked first recognition and affiliation of the institute following the quality of education and placement assistance as their second and third priority while information search about a college.

Table 4 Decision Factors

	Fre que ncy	Perc ent	Valid Percen t	Cumul ative Percen t
College of Parents' Choice				
Most likely	176	35.2	35.2	35.2
Likely	139	27.8	27.8	63.0
May be	121	24.2	24.2	87.2
Never	64	12.8	12.8	100.0
College of Friends' Choice				
Most likely	231	46.2	46.2	46.2
Likely	103	20.6	20.6	66.8
May be	87	17.4	17.4	84.2
Never	79	15.8	15.8	100.0
College with similar culture				
Strongly Agree	165	33.0	33.0	33.0
Agree	213	42.6	42.6	75.6
Neutral	24	4.8	4.8	80.4
Disagree	76	15.2	15.2	95.6
Strongly Disagree	22	4.4	4.4	100.0

Table 4 shows that the final decision of selecting institute from all available institutions meeting the basic criteria as found in the above results also depends upon some psychological factors like College of Parents' Choice (315 i.e. 63% of total respondents), College of Friends' Choice (334 i.e. 66.6% of total respondents) and College with similar culture (378 i.e. 75.6% of total respondents).

8. Conclusion

Today, recent business marketing approaches that depend upon market analysis and planning have stimulated the growth of marketing firms that offer sophisticated quantitative market analyses in order to identify an organization's potential and current customers and their needs. Students characteristics, external influences, college attributes and information satisfaction are the factors that influence the student's choices of college. Variables which normally students are

considering at the time of college search are college reputation, educational facilities, employment opportunities, friends attending college and influence of other individuals.

Apart from the above factors parent pressure and cultural similarities also have significant impact in the decision of selecting an institute. Using the factors mentioned above, colleges could re-strategies their marketing strategies in order to attract and retain students. What we have observed that educational Institutions must seriously looks at issues we have found and the important one is that the marketers must consider proper segmentation strategies to target the actual students (prospects). Educational Services are being consumed by students while the actual buyers are the parents who are actually paying fees of the courses. So, it becomes equally important to consider parents in designing marketing mix at a given situation. The cultural and social factors also do impact the decision of the students regarding the selection of educational Institutions.

9. Recommendations

- **Accountability to Third-Party**

Institutions must maintain credibility with parents, donors, alumni, employers and other stake holders

- **Reduce Uncertainty**

It's documented that consumers of highly priced items can feel buyer's remorse, so most salespeople follow up shortly after the sale to ensure customers are comfortable with their decision and to counteract any extreme fears. After a student makes the major decision about which college to attend, key units within the university, such as student development, the business office and the academic department, must maintain contact to reinforce that the student's decision was wise and valid. Little or no contact between the time of acceptance and reporting for class can result in a student changing his or her mind.

- **Encourage World Class Experience**

The university's "brand" is based on quality, which often translates into faculty with vast teaching experience. However, especially in business-related disciplines, this must also translate into real-world experiences. Marketers must be able to accurately convey this balance.

- **Differentiate your offerings**

Although colleges know they must find the unique attributes that make their institution distinctive, claims for institutions within the same category, such as faith-based liberal arts colleges, may sound very similar: "academic rigor, personal attention, and the teaching of values and ethics."

- **Maintaining Quality Control**

All service industries experience variability in quality control because the humans delivering the service can be inconsistent transaction to transaction and person to person. Quality at a university

depends not only on behavior and competence of all faculty and staff it depends on the behavior of the students who become alumni – a key indicator of reputation.

- **Allocating Faculty and Staff Time to Marketing**

Even if faculty is resistant the university will benefit from a culture shift toward involving everyone in marketing efforts to the extent that this expectation is made explicit in job descriptions.

- **Reorienting the Reactive to the Proactive**

The orientation of most institutions of higher education is naturally reactive rather than proactive...In most colleges and universities, marketers are tasked with marketing the institution as it is. *This is who we are and what we offer*, administrators tell the marketers. *Promote it*.

- **Conflicting Views on Advertising**

Traditionally, some in higher education equate marketing with advertising and feel that at the worst, advertising cheapens the university image and puts it on par with for-profit educational institutions. At the best, it wastes scarce institutional resources that could be channeled toward academic programs. Others believe it is a valuable tool for educating potential students and donors about the university's benefits.

- **A Limited Marketing Knowledge Base**

Every faculty and staff member must have a basic grasp of marketing principles to achieve the levels of service required to effectively market the university. He contends that marketers in general do not have solid base of knowledge regarding the marketing of services and that higher education is even more specialized. Marketers who come from an environment of marketing goods must become familiar with the politics and stakeholder groups in an academic setting. Likewise, faculty and staff who have had no exposure to marketing concepts need basic training.

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